

Communications Strategy

Deliverable 6.1

Deliverable description

Deliverable 6.1 explains the rationale, steps and tools that will be put in place and developed for effective Communication and Dissemination of the IMPETUS project. It presents the strategies that will be undertaken to reach target audiences, to reach the milestones and promote the results of the project.

To be quoted as:

Troncoso, A. EUSEA, 2022. "IMPETUS Project: Communications Strategy".

Deliverable	D6.1 Communications strategy
Work Package	6 - Dissemination and communications
Due of Deliverable	30. 11. 2022
Lead beneficiary of this deliverable	EUSEA - European Science Engagement Association
Version	V1.0
Author(s) and Institution(s)	Andrea Troncoso - EUSEA
Submission Date	30.11.2022
Reviewers	Joana Magalhães, Science for Change (SfC)

PU	Public	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CI	Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	

The information, documentation and figures in this deliverable are written by the IMPETUS project Consortium. They do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

IMPETUS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon WIDERA 2021-ERA-01 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 101058677

Table of contents

Summary	6
1. Introduction	7
2. Acronyms	9
3. Overview of the project	10
4. Work Package 6 Objectives	11
4.1 Partners' roles and workflow	12
5. Target audiences and messages	13
5.1 Target audiences	13
Citizens	14
Researchers/Innovators	14
Policymakers, civil servants, funding agencies	15
Business	15
Science data journalists	15
CS associations, platforms and umbrella organisations	16
Figure 1: Target groups of stakeholders for the IMPETUS Project	16
5.2 Key messages	16
6. Communication strategy	17
6.1. Communication objectives	17
6.2 Communication phases	17
6.3 Guiding principles	18
7. Dissemination strategy	19
7.1 Dissemination objectives	20
7.2. Guiding Principles	20
8. Tools and channels	20
8.1 Visual identity	20
8.2 Website	21
8.3 Social media	22
8.4 ZENODO	23
8.5 Promotional materials for open calls and annual prizes	23
8.6 Publications	24
8.7 Infographics	25
9. Events	26
9.1 IMPETUS Final conference	26

9.2 External events	27
10. Monitoring: KPIs	28
11. Final remarks	29

Summary

Deliverable 6.1 presents the work plan for WP6 'Dissemination and Communications'.

The main objective of this Work Package is to raise awareness of the three Open Calls for the IMPETUS Accelerator program and the European Union Prize for Citizen Science. It also aims at communicating the activities and outcomes of IMPETUS and its Accelerator pilots, providing promotional material, and engaging with relevant stakeholders.

It presents the target audiences, strategies and relevant messages that the Consortium will convey along the project's timeline. This component is followed by a comprehensive list of relevant steps that will be undertaken for communication and dissemination activities.. This plan represents a roadmap to boost the visibility of project's activities, milestones and outcomes.

This document is the first deliverable assigned to WP6, Dissemination & Communication, led by EUSEA, the European Science Engagement Association.

1. Introduction

“Great communication begins with connection”

Oprah Winfrey, television producer and host, author, philanthropist

Communicating effectively the results of a EU-funded project is a relevant component of its success. It contributes to enhancing the impact of EU funding, while building a stronger sense of an European community.

This Communication Strategy, which includes Dissemination actions, C&D, aims to establish the tools and the relevant steps to support the communication of the project and boost awareness of it amongst diverse audiences. The objectives of this plan are, on one hand, to provide a practical set of instruments and guidelines for the Consortium as a whole, to help them identify and exploit communication opportunities along the project's timeline. The strategy foresees to streamline different actions that will be implemented at the local, national, European and international levels.

This plan will be reviewed twice a year, taking into account qualitative and quantitative data related to online and offline communication activities carried out. Based on this, adaptations may occur, in order to fine-tune with the encountered needs.

Communication and dissemination are central to Horizon Europe framework projects, and together with the exploitation of results, have different objectives, focus and target audiences. Based on an early H2020 EC document, the following definitions will be considered as guiding concepts¹:

¹ *Making the most of your H2020 Project. Boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation.* European IPR Helpdesk, 2018.
http://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/sites/default/files/EU-IPR-Brochure-Boosting-Impact-C-D-E_0.pdf

- Communication: aimed at reaching out to society and showing the impact and benefits of the project to them; the main focus is to inform about and promote the project and its results/success; it is addressed to multiple audiences beyond the project's own community, including media and the broad public.
- Dissemination: aimed at transferring knowledge and results, enabling others to use them; is focused on describing and ensuring results available for others to use; it is addressed to audiences that potentially can use the results.
- Exploitation: concerns the effective use of project results, turning them into concrete value and impact for society; it focuses on making concrete use of the results; it is addressed to anyone using the results inside and outside the project.

2. Acronyms

EU	European Union
CS	Citizen Science
CSIs	Citizen Science Initiatives
GD	Green Deal
UN SDG	United Nations Sustainable Development Goals
EUSEA	European Science Engagement Association
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
WP	Work Package
EUPCS	European Union Prize for Citizen Science

3. Overview of the project

IMPETUS will support and give recognition to citizen science by enabling a wider range of citizen science initiatives to access innovative funding.

It aims to bring CS closer to quadruple helix stakeholders, including society, academia, industry and policymakers, as well as the science communication and journalism professionals and the cultural and creative sector, and to acknowledge its role in tackling the greatest challenges of our times. It will have a strong focus on enhancing its contributions to the Green Deal and the UN SDGs.

IMPETUS four main objectives are:

- (O1) Opening routes to funding for a more diverse range of CSIs.
- (O2) Strengthening the bond between society and science.
- (O3) Recognising the role of citizen science in Europe.
- (O4) Enhancing the contribution of CS to achieving SDG and GD targets.

The support to the Citizen Science Initiatives will be achieved through:

1. Three Open Calls, selecting the initiatives based on expected impacts, volunteer engagement, EDI, openness and quality data. 20k to kick-start 100 CSIs and 10k will be offered to sustain 25 CSIs addressing the pressing needs of European society.
2. Setting up an Accelerator programme that will provide an integrated programme of support, training, mentoring, and resources. The Accelerator will facilitate peer learning, enable CSIs to contribute to UN SDG and GD targets and forge connections with [quadruple helix](#) stakeholders.

3. Launching the EU Prize for Citizen Science, awarded to CSIs for outstanding achievements, allowing them to continue and expand their work and showcase it to a broader audience. There will be 3 prize categories during 3 years: outstanding achievements, diversity and innovative grassroots projects. Each time, advisors will be reached out to identify exceptional nominations and to the citizen panel to vote in the grassroots category.
4. Convening a citizen panel that provides feedback on IMPETUS work.
5. Shaping EU policy in and with CS, through Horizon scanning, anticipatory policy and action research, informing policy briefs, webinars and workshops with key policy stakeholders. The aim is to foster more CS data to inform evidence-based policies and identify future directions in CS policy.
6. Developing impact assessment tools and assessing the impact of CSIs and our own framework, especially on GD and SDG targets. Insights will be presented within the wider CS ecosystem and feed into recommendations for national and EU policies.

4. Work Package 6 Objectives

The main objective of this WP is to raise awareness on the Open Calls and Prize, communicate the activities and outcomes of IMPETUS and its pilots, provide promotional material, andThe engage with relevant stakeholders.

The Communication and dissemination strategy that will be described in the following sections has three goals:

- (i) raise awareness of our work and the work of CSIs;
- (ii) communicate key achievements and progress; and

(iii) make these achievements available and accessible to different stakeholders e.g. researchers, creatives, artists, and other professionals, as well as for-profit, governmental, and not-profit organisations.

The strategy will focus on the main streams of work in the project:

- (i) the open calls;
- (ii) the accelerator and its CSIs;
- (iii) the European Union Prize for Citizen Science

It will also support the dissemination of evidence-based policy recommendations and results from the impact assessment.

4.1 Partners' roles and workflow

EUSEA leads the WP on Dissemination & Communication activities in close collaboration with the Coordination team, in order to adapt to specific communication needs that could arise along the implementation of the project. Communicating effectively also means regularly interacting with the project partners, therefore regular meetings will be scheduled, which will provide the whole Consortium with an overview of activities already implemented or to implement. To boost synergies, the management of the social media channels will be coordinated by EUSEA but decentralised, allowing each partner to communicate in an autonomous way relevant actions. They will be involved through their own and institutional social media.

5. Target audiences and messages

IMPETUS will communicate its progress and disseminate news and results to a broad range of stakeholders or audiences. All these represent target audiences to be informed about the calls, the accelerator, the EUPCS and the relevance of CS, through CSIs news stories and impact findings.

5.1 Target audiences

Citizens interested in participating in CS: will be targeted for promoting the possibility of engaging with pilot projects and taking part in activities, they will be informed about the IMPETUS bootcamp and the possibility to participate in the selection of Open Calls' topics and be part of the Prize's jury.

Researchers/innovators working on topics related to the ones tackled by IMPETUS and citizens/communities engaged or interested in CS will be informed about the open calls, the IMPETUS virtual bootcamp, our success stories (source of inspiration to implement CS projects), key findings and events (networking and matchmaking).

Policy makers, civic servants, funding agencies will be targeted for the CS prize, demonstrating the role CS can have in supporting evidence-based policymaking. They will be informed about IMPETUS pilots and experimental methodologies to be implemented and scaled-up at the local level, as well as about policy workshops and seminars in WP4. Finally, this group will also be the main recipients for the policy briefs and considered in the CSIs individual impact assessment reports.

CS associations, platforms and umbrella organisations, CS-or topic-related EU projects will be reached for promoting project main findings and IMPETUS events. They will be also engaged within WP2 to support networking and reciprocal learning with the selected CSIs, together with **science and data journalists** and **businesses** in relevant sectors.

For fulfilling this mission, a range of tools on multiple channels will be deployed, bespoke for each audience and monitored on how effective they are in achieving the expected outcomes and impacts. Some of the indicators and target numbers to help monitor the impact of such activities are listed in section 10 of this document. For the purpose of this guiding document, the following broad definitions are considered:

Citizens

This multifaceted group is essentially linked to the ambition of the project to implement actions synergically in their respective territories. They are non-academic researchers with an important interest in science. They are involved in CS projects or have the will to.

Example of message to deliver to this group:

- Understanding scientific data is a skill for making informed choices in daily life

Researchers/Innovators

Academic scientists include researchers that work in universities, science and technology parks, technology transfer offices, units of scientific cultures and research centres. This large and diverse community includes both researchers who participate in CS projects and who are sceptical about them.

Example of message to deliver to this group:

- CS can be as rigorous and trustworthy as academic science

Polymakers, civil servants, funding agencies

Policy-maker² is a broad term that covers all the people responsible for formulating or amending policy. It can include Ministers, their advisers, civil servants, officially appointed Chief Scientific Advisers, Parliamentary Committee members, and all of their advisory staff. It can also include the staff of government national and/or local agencies, who have expert knowledge in a particular area and tend to play a role in informing the policy making process. Another example are the local bodies contributing to the monitoring of the SDGs.

Example of message to deliver to this group:

- CS projects can involve and engage a community to work together with a public administration

Business

This target audience includes entrepreneurs, research & development, or innovation departments at universities or institutes, SMEs or big companies.

Example of message to deliver to this group:

- CS can be a stepping stone to innovation

Science communicators and journalists

They are communicators and/or journalists specialised in science and data journalism in the field of science. Data journalism or data-driven journalism (DDJ) is a journalistic process based on analysing and filtering large data sets for the purpose of creating or elevating a news story³.

Example of message to deliver to this group:

- CS delivers data that highlights new trends

² This definition was adapted from the one presented on the NCCPE: <https://www.publicengagement.ac.uk/do-engagement/understanding-audiences/policy-makers>

³ Wikipedia: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Data_journalism

□ CS associations, platforms and umbrella organisations

They are communities gathered around CS in a territorial or disciplinary way. They might belong to a network or to an EU-funded project. They are in permanent contact and there is a communication flow among them.

Example of message to deliver to this group:

- CS projects can boost the impact of your collaborative actions

Figure 1: Target groups of stakeholders for the IMPETUS Project

5.2 Key messages

IMPETUS will define in detail the messages for each of the target audiences through an empathy-map exercise, to be executed in the coming month with all partners.. General communication activities will focus on the following messages:

- (i) CS can support evidence-based policymaking;
- (ii) CS can open up and energise local innovation ecosystems;
- (iii) cities and regions can benefit from CS practices;

- (iv) CS can help address complex local and global challenges, and support SDG and Green Deal reporting;
- (v) CS can make science and innovation more democratic, by being open and inclusive;
- (vi) CS can help regain people's trust in science;
- (vii) CS can help reach out to under-served audiences;
- (viii) CS is solid science and should be used routinely.
- (ix) Science is a common good
- (x) CS can boost innovation

6. Communication strategy

Communication is aimed at informing a wider audience about the project. Here, an overview of the objectives of communication activities to be carried on, its phases as well as the guiding principles.

6.1. Communication objectives

- To enhance the visibility of IMPETUS goals, activities and outcomes, along its implementation;
- To bring attention to the three Open Calls;
- To raise awareness about the European Union Prize for Citizen Science
- To strengthen the understanding of CS by the wider society;
- To communicate the benefits of citizen science;

All the above will contribute to the global positioning of the European CS ecosystem.

6.2 Communication phases

The flow of the activities for communication will be a spiral one, that will repeat every time a new call is launched. We identify the following phases:

- The first phase (M1-12) July 2022-June 2023 encompasses the beginning of the project and the development of the Communication Strategy and to design the first communication materials to be deployed during the first Open Call to be launched during January 2023.
- The second phase (M13-25) is focused on reaching IMPETUS stakeholders with the learnings and outcomes from the first Open Call. Networking activities with other related EU projects will be crucial for creating synergies and boosting the dissemination. The European Union Prize for Citizen Science is also part of the core message to disseminate.
- The third phase (M26-38) focuses on the learning of the two previous calls and the preparation for the last Open Call. The European Union Prize for Citizen Science focuses its action to its installation and to the reflection and designing of a legacy action plan for sustainability. Dissemination and communication are focused on maintaining stakeholders engagement.
- The fourth phase (M38-48) is focused on disseminating the final results of the project and promoting their dissemination and exploitation.

After each call is closed and communication actions are performed, EUSEA will reflect on possible adjustments for the next phases.

6.3 Guiding principles

- Storytelling connects

Storytelling is a long-term communication strategy building both empathy and trust. It is a two-way interaction, written or oral, between someone telling a story and one or more listeners. It is a well-known and powerful means of communicating messages and engaging audiences. An increasing number of studies are showing how narratives can be useful for developing trust with an audience and increasing knowledge retention as well as the ability and

willingness by audiences to learn and take action⁴. Communicating evidence in an understandable and practically relevant way for stakeholders, for instance by embedding knowledge in a narrative storyline, has shown to increase audience's engagement, as well as willingness to act upon the knowledge and use the evidence as a basis for decisions. IMPETUS will regularly communicate about the stories behind the call, behind the CSIs, providing catchy content and communicating on the progress via a storytelling approach.

- Engaging is a set of actions

Engaging means creating content that solicits active participation of the both parties involved. It not only helps to gain the attention of the target groups, but it also helps to get them interested and entertain regular exchanges.

- Communicate visually

Visual communication, which is based on the use of visual elements, such as drawings, illustrations and digital images, certainly has made it easy to explain, understand and remember information that is relevant to us. IMPETUS will thoughtfully use images in order to foster general understanding while creating compelling messages.

Source: Killer infographics

⁴ https://jcom.sissa.it/archive/18/06/JCOM_1806_2019_A02

7. Dissemination strategy

Dissemination is aimed at sharing and enabling the access to the information about the project, results and outcomes. For achieving this goal, effective communication products and sound channels are key.

7.1 Dissemination objectives

1. Provide tools to effectively disseminate the outcomes of IMPETUS during all its phases
2. Continuous reflection on the channels and audience reception to the dissemination actions deployed.

7.2. Guiding Principles

IMPETUS dissemination strategy will build on four guiding principles that will lead the whole set of dissemination actions to be implemented along the project's timeline. These guiding principles are listed below:

- Efficiency: IMPETUS activities carried out will be interpreted and used as an occasion for dissemination, meaning that dissemination activities will take advantage, wherever possible, of transversal activities stemming from the diverse project's components;
- Relevance: Dissemination activities will not be considered as a linear process in which a partner delivers inputs to single targets.
- Effectiveness. Dissemination targets will not be passive receivers of information. The project will trigger stakeholders' engagement and encourage participation to make knowledge sharing more effective;
- Feasibility. The dissemination activities will be planned, coordinated, monitored and supported by pertinent measures so as to ensure that planned objectives are met.

8. Tools and channels

8.1 Visual identity

IMPETUS visual identity includes a logo, branding guidelines, templates for internal communication and external communication activities. The brand guideline is available here: [IMPETUS Branding Guidelines 2022](#)

Brand Guidelines.

October 2022

Version_01

8.2 Website

The IMPETUS website was launched in October 2022 and it represents the main window for communication and dissemination actions. At this first stage it shows a simple menu that will get more complex as the different phases of the project unfold. Deliverable 6.2 explains its rational and production.

[Home](#) [About](#) [Prizes categories](#) [Contact us](#)

New pages will include the open calls, the accelerator, the funded CSIs, the prize, a repository of learning resources (virtual bootcamp), our publications

and deliverables, news from the CSIs, as well dashboards with open call stats and impact data.

The website will feature a virtual bootcamp containing freely accessible education resources. Some of these will be created for the accelerator in WP2, others will be from prior or related projects of the IMPETUS consortium and our collaborations, including the updated ACTION toolkit (see also Section 2.2.3), the Collective Intelligence Design Playbook, D-NOSES and NEWSERA. Smooth alignment, cross reference, and cross-pollination with the EU.Citizen-Science platform will be constantly pursued.

8.3 Social media

Social media is a tool and channel that needs constant dedication and observation of its results. IMPETUS will focus its efforts in its own Twitter, LinkedIn and [YouTube](#) account. We consider using advertising and campaigns to promote the calls and major milestones.

- Twitter: <http://twitter.com/impetus4cs>

List of IMPETUS hashtags: #CitizenScience, #CitSci, #CitSciComm, #Swafs

- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/impetus4cs>

- Other social media accounts

Partners will be encouraged to use and share information about the project through their institutional Facebook and Instagram accounts.

8.4 ZENODO

Zenodo is a general-purpose open repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. It allows researchers to deposit research papers, data sets, research software, reports, and any other research related digital artefacts. IMPETUS will create an account and a community to make its reports, results and communication materials available here, expanding the reach beyond the website. A link to Zenodo will appear on the website.

8.5 Promotional materials for open calls and annual prizes

- **Open calls:** IMPETUS will develop and produce an array of promotional material. This is a non-exhaustive list. The calls will be published in the second week of each January and close in mid-March. A calendar with the materials and the date of production will be

created in the projects shared folder, to ensure these materials will be timely in place.

1. Digital postcards
 2. PPT presentations presenting the call
 3. A dedicated section on the website as well as promotional banners will be produced with the support of a professional designer and circulated amongst the partners.
- **The prize:** As the Prize asks for already realised projects (and not the development of proposals), experience has shown that this period is best to keep the attention high.

Prior to the call closure a) a press release will be issued, b) the website will be updated, c) several newsletters for call information & attraction of submitters will be distributed, d) blog interviews with experts in the field of CS, or nominating advisors/jurors will be posted, e) extensive social media (partly paid via advertisements and a dedicated media partner) will be campaigned and e) information material will be distributed to relevant communities (which will be further addressed in the research phase).

After the jury meeting the Prize Winners will be published online and in print, on the website, starts.eu, in the archive, on social media and via blogs and videos to intensify the impact for the next launch.

Promotion of the Prize: Specific activities aiming to promote the Prize will be implemented. In this framework, an effort to target traditional media will be done, alongside with an effort to reach international communities interested in the topics tackled by the project in order to: i) nurture recognition of CS; ii) promote sustainability and scaling-up

8.6 Publications

- **Policy briefs** will be promoted and disseminated to decision makers by participating in at least 3 events explicitly targeting this audience, especially local administrators, These outputs will be available on the website as well as promoted via social media.
- **Scientific articles** stemming from project activities, e.g. the action research in WP4, or the impact assessment methodology from WP5, will be available as open access and submitted to conferences and journals.
- **Press releases** will be issued at key milestones (open calls, accelerator launches, prize) to boost visibility and reach traditional media. The press releases will be part of a comprehensive media relations strategy, whose purpose will be soliciting the attention of media, building trustful relationships with them, and boosting visibility to attract applicants to the accelerator and prize.
- **Newsletters** IMPETUS will create a newsletter that will keep its publics informed. It will also scan other newsletters, where its information can be disseminated. As an example, ECSA newsletter will be approached, so the reach will increase significantly.

For all these activities and audiences, we will be seeking to collaborate with other European and national programmes and to key CS stakeholders to build a stronger sense of community and exploit synergies, including ECSA, European Citizen.Science, the SwafS projects, the We Observe communities, national/regional hubs for CS, and the EC (for the annual CS prize). We will foster ties with the ENJOI observatory to engage with science journalists, science communicators, and experts in civic engagement. IMPETUS will execute a mapping exercise to clearly identify the stakeholders and the degree of connections and possible synergies.

8.7 Infographics

A set of infographics for dissemination purposes will be developed at different stages of the project. During the month of November a calendar with the needs for infographics will be set by the partners.

9. Events

The project will participate in several events to present the programme and its achievements, including a demo day following each accelerator where the projects present their work to the public. Partners will ensure coverage in their respective countries and take part in events to localise communication efforts and, where applicable, tailor and present results to specialist audiences e.g. policy stakeholders, digital innovation hubs, smart cities etc.

This will include conferences where we will present our publications (see below External events), as well as other events with speaking opportunities.

IMPETUS will run:

- a) Invitation-only events in several work packages to support key activities around the open calls' definition with the citizen panel, the prize winners award ceremony at Ars Electronica.
- b) Webinars and workshops with policy stakeholders in WP4.

9.1 IMPETUS Final conference

A final event will be organised that aims to disseminate the products and results, interact with a wider community and to showcase key findings and CSIs. The organisation of this event will be led by Ars Electronica with the collaboration of EUSEA and all partners. The place and date will be discussed among the Consortium. It will take place between March- June 2026.

9.2 External events

Networking and liaising with international communities are core activities for strengthening all communication and dissemination efforts. Coordinated

actions will be deployed for liaising and networking with international CS communities, such as European Citizen.Science, ECSA, CS observatories and similar communities of practice, to build a sustainable legacy, promote the sharing of good practices, boost visibility and ensure a successful positioning of IMPETUS. The European and global ecosystem tackling issues that pilots work on will also be addressed.

The consortium will participate in external events (both online and physical) to promote the activities of the project while raising awareness of the benefits of CS. An initial list of events are the following:

- ECSA Conference
- EU projects conferences and workshops
- EUSEA Conference
- ECSITE conference
- EU National conferences
- Collective Intelligence Conference
- International Conference on Social Entrepreneurship and Innovation
- SDGs local conferences
- The European Week of Cities and Regions
- Open and Agile Smart Cities
- New Scientist Research Festival of Trieste

All partners will be involved to ensure visibility in respective countries and other easily reachable international areas. Policy papers generated by WP4 will be promoted during these events.

10. Monitoring: KPIs

The following table shows the KPIs that IMPETUS will be monitoring to get the pulse of its actions and correct, boost or create the measures for ensuring the reach of its target numbers.

Objectives	Strategies	KP1	KP2	KP3
Enhance the visibility of IMPETUS	Offline and online outreach	Online reach omni-channel 20,000+	100+ newsletter subscribers	5,000 website visits/year
Raise awareness of the relevance of CS	Messages and outputs disseminated via project's channels	Annual social media activities: 150+ tweets & 30+ LinkedIn posts	Min. 5 videos	50+ news published on new and traditional media
Engage target audiences	Offline and online outreach building on specific topics	250+ targeted emails / year	Annual prize ceremony (3 in total) w/ 1500 guests from quadruplex helix stakeholders, 100k visitors	3 online demo days as final events of the acceleration
Develop comprehensive set of materials to ensure results delivery	Attractive design, products tailored to consortium's needs	3+ appearance in newsletters/year	3+ press releases/year	5 videos in 3 years
Leverage and harness the dissemination channels	Tailored messaging and latest CSI news	100+ mailing list subscribers	Offline communication reports	Online communication reports
Establish conditions for a robust legacy	Targeted networking, high-quality content	Attendance of 10+ conferences, scientific and policy events/year	5+ open access publications in conferences or journals	Website section with IMPETUS knowledge products

11. Final remarks

This plan is a roadmap document. Its implementation will be based on the coordinated work of all partners. It will be revised and adjusted to fit the current needs and external situations that may come. Therefore, it should be considered as a living document.

